

Oxidimetric Determination of 2-Mercaptopyrimidines by Periodate

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A new oxidimetric method is reported for the determination of 2-mercaptopyrimidines in acid medium using potassium or sodium periodate as the oxidant. Each mole of the periodate oxidises 8 moles of the mercaptopyrimidine quantitatively.

VARIOUS oxidimetric methods have been worked out for the determination of 2-mercaptopyrimidines¹. These methods make use of the quantitative oxidation of the thiol group to disulphide group with suitable oxidants. Mercaptopyrimidines have also been determined by silver nitrate².

The present investigation reports the use of potassium or sodium periodate for the quantitative oxidation of 2-mercaptopyrimidines in sulphuric acid medium. The oxidation proceeds very smoothly and rapidly. The procedure, is simple, accurate, and the determination is direct.

- a, R = hydrogen
- b, R = methyl group
- c, R = *n*-butyl group
- d, R = iso-butyl group
- e, R = phenyl group
- f, R = 3-nitrophenyl group
- g, R = 2-nitro-4-methylphenyl group

Experimental

Mercaptopyrimidines were prepared by the method of Mathes³ and purified by repeated crystallisations from suitable solvents.

A standard (0.01 *M*) solution of potassium periodate was prepared by dissolving 2.300 g of the dried compound in water and making the volume to 1 litre. In the case of sodium periodate 2.1390 g of the compound was weighed for making one litre of 0.01*M* solution in water. Both of these solutions were standardised by titrating with a known weight (50–100 mg) of thiourea AR in 1 *N* sulphuric acid using amylose as indicator.

1% aqueous solution of amylose was used as an indicator in all titrations.

Procedure :

A known wt. (10–100 mg) of 2-mercaptopyrimidines (a–f) was dissolved in 18*N* sulphuric acid (3–5 ml) and sufficient water (24–85 ml) added to bring the normality of the solution between 1–2*N* in acid. The compound g was dissolved in 5 ml of dimethylformamide and then the requisite amount of sulphuric acid and water were added in order to adjust the normality of the solution with respect to the acid at 1–2*N*. The solution in each case was cooled to room temperature and titrated against 0.01*M* potassium periodate. The end point was detected visually by using amylose (0.2 to 0.5 ml) as an internal indicator; the solution acquired a blue colour at the end point.

TABLE 1. DETERMINATION OF 2-MERCAPTOPYRIMIDINES BY POTASSIUM PERIODATE (0.01*M*)

Sl.No.	Compound	Taken mg	Found mg
1.	a, R = hydrogen	10.2	10.234
2.	b, R = methyl group	78.0	77.520
3.	c, R = <i>n</i> -butyl group	50.0	49.862
4.	d, R = iso-butyl group	65.4	65.006
5.	e, R = phenyl group	37.6	37.488
6.	f, R = 3-nitrophenyl group	19.8	19.634
7.	g, R = 2-nitro-4-methylphenyl group	22.0	21.812

From the volume of the standard potassium periodate consumed, corresponding to the end point in each titration, the amount of each compound was calculated. One mole of periodate was consumed per 8 moles of 2-mercaptopyrimidine.

The titrations were repeated in a similar manner with 0.01*M* sodium periodate.

The results of our experiments (Table 1) show that the above mentioned 2-mercaptopyrimidines (a–g)

can be determined by direct titrations with either potassium periodate or sodium periodate (both 0.01*M*) in the range of 10–100 mg with an accuracy of $\pm 1\%$.

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References

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